

Data Protection Policy for Monitoring EOSC Readiness in the EOSC Open Science Observatory

V3.0 on 16 June 2025

Personal Data Policy

OpenAIRE (henceforth the 'Data Controller') considers the protection and security of Personal Data as a high priority and responsibility towards the Open Science community. This Data Protection Policy is in place to protect the Personal Data of (designated representatives of) the members of the EOSC Steering Board using the EOSC Open Science Observatory [<https://www.eoscobservatory.eu/>]. The Data Controller recognises the right to the protection of Personal Data and ensures the application of the current legal framework (in particular Regulation 2016/679 and the respective national laws). The EOSC Open Science Observatory is being developed by OpenAIRE as an activity in the EOSC Track project [<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101148217>]. As a user of the EOSC Open Science Observatory and our services, you must be aware that your Personal Data is collected and maintained by the Data Controller for a certain period of time and for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes. Personal Data shall be treated fairly and in a transparent manner in accordance with the applicable legal framework and in such a way as to guarantee their security. Information regarding the processing of such data may be found in the respective sections below.

Data Controller

The Data Controller for the purpose of the operation of the EOSC Open Science Observatory and the provision of the services listed below is as follows:

**OpenAIRE AMKE
Artemidos 6
1512 Maroussi, Greece**

OpenAIRE is responsible for the design and direction of the processing of the Personal Data and nonpersonal data as well as the technical collection, presentation, transfer, and storage of the Personal Data and non-personal data in the EOSC Open Science Observatory.

The Data Controller may modify this policy to achieve a better protection of Personal Data by announcing such modifications via the EOSC Open Science Observatory, by demarcating and dating the versions, and by keeping an archive of previous Data Protection Policies on the EOSC Open Science Observatory website.

By navigating and using the EOSC Open Science Observatory, visitors/users acknowledge that they have read, understood, and unconditionally accepted this Data Protection Policy.

For further information, you may contact the Data Protection Officer of the Data Controller by sending an e-mail to <dpo@openaire.eu>.

Data Processor

All data collected by the Data Controller are processed in terms of storage space and preservation in accordance with this Data Protection Policy and under the instructions of the Data Controllers by:

**ICM, University of Warsaw
26/28 Street Krakowskie Przedmieście,
00-927 Warsaw, Poland**

Purpose of Personal Data Processing

The processing of Personal Data means any operation or set of operations that is performed on Personal Data or on sets of Personal Data, whether or not by automated means, including collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction of the Personal Data.

The Personal Data identified in the following section are processed for the purpose of collecting, analysing, and presenting data on the monitoring of EOSC readiness of Member States and Associated Countries via the EOSC Open Science Observatory. The monitoring data will be collected via surveys that are completed internally in the EOSC Open Science Observatory by (designated representatives of) the members of the EOSC Steering Board. This non-personal monitoring data will be shared via the EOSC Open Science Observatory.

Personal Data

'Personal Data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. An identifiable natural person (known as the 'Data Subject') is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier, including a name, identification number, location data, online identifier (such as an IP or e-mail address), or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person.

We obtain the following Personal Data from the OpenAIRE AAI when a user logs in to the EOSC Open Science Observatory:

- First name
- Last name
- Full name
- Email address
- OpenAIRE AAI unique identifier

We also associate the following Personal Data that have been shared in agreement with the Data Controllers by the EOSC Steering Board with users of the EOSC Open Science Observatory:

- Status as member of the EOSC Steering Board
- Name of Member State or Associated Country

Recipients of the Personal Data

Designated OpenAIRE administrators will have access to the Personal Data in order to perform necessary activities for the processing of the collected monitoring data. A log will be kept and will be made accessible if required by law or contract upon request.

Personal Data may also be shared with (designated representatives of) the members of the EOSC Steering Board for the processing and validation of the collected monitoring data. The Data Controllers will in this case transfer the relevant Personal Data and enter into a Data Controller to Controller relationship with the EOSC Steering Board. Due diligence will be performed to ensure that the EOSC Steering Board has adequate Personal Data policies in place before transferring the Personal Data. A log will be kept and will be made accessible if required by law or contract upon request.

Personal Data Retention

All Personal Data obtained for the purposes of the monitoring of EOSC readiness via the EOSC Open Science Observatory will be kept for a period of six months after completion of the EOSC Track project.

Personal Data Security

To protect the privacy of users of the EOSC Open Science Observatory, we employ data security measures to prevent the loss, misuse, unauthorised access, and disclosure of collected Personal Data.

Access to your Personal Data is restricted to authorised representatives of OpenAIRE, ICM, and the EOSC Steering Board who have a duty of confidentiality.

Your Rights

As far as the protection of your Personal Data is concerned, you have the following rights:

- The right of access to your Personal Data
- The right of correction of your Personal Data
- The right of remission of your Personal Data
- The right to limit processing of your Personal Data
- The right of portability of your Personal Data
- The right to object to the processing of your Personal Data.

To exercise your rights, you may contact the Data Protection Officer of OpenAIRE by sending an e-mail to <dpo@openaire.eu>.

[Right of Termination](#)

If a user believes that the protection of their Personal Data is at risk or that the Data Controller has not adequately responded, then the user may contact relevant Personal Data Protection Authorities:

Hellenic Data Protection Authority

Kifissias 1-3

PC 115 23, Athens, Greece

Telephone: +302106475600

E-mail: <contact@dpa.gr>

Website: [<https://www.dpa.gr/en>]

[Privacy Policy Version](#)

This is Version 3.0 of this Privacy Policy as of 16 June 2025.